

Heavy Metals and Human Health: From Neurological Disorders to Developmental Delays

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Abstract

This review discusses the significant health risks posed by exposure to environmentally toxic heavy metals such as lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel. These metals can cause severe and sometimes irreversible damage to various organs and systems in the human body. Each metal has specific health impacts, including neurological disorders, renal and cardiovascular diseases, developmental delays, and cancers. The paper highlights the ability of these metals to cross the placental barrier, affecting fetal development and resulting in adverse pregnancy outcomes like preterm birth, low birth weight, and developmental issues. Heavy metals disrupt placental function by inducing oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and impaired nutrient and oxygen transport, leading to long-term health consequences for the offspring. The paper also explores how heavy metal exposure can cause epigenetic changes, altering gene expression and contributing to chronic diseases. Some of these effects can be transmitted across generations. The contamination of pharmaceuticals and natural remedies with heavy metals is also a concern, emphasizing the need for rigorous quality control and regulatory oversight to protect public health. Diagnostic procedures for detecting heavy metal exposure involve comprehensive history-taking, physical examinations, laboratory tests, neuroimaging, and assessments of neurological and motor functions. The paper underscores the importance of addressing environmental exposure to toxic heavy metals to mitigate their harmful impacts and safeguard public health.

Keywords: *Chelation, Good Manufacturing Practices, Placenta Barrier, Spirulina, Toxic Heavy Metals.*

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Introduction

Essential Heavy Metals

The human body requires essential heavy metals in small amounts for various physiological and biochemical functions. The most important ones include iron, zinc, copper, manganese, molybdenum, cobalt (as part of vitamin B12), and chromium. The following is a detailed look at each essential heavy metal.

Iron (Fe)

- **Why Essential:** Iron is crucial for oxygen transport (as a component of hemoglobin), electron transfer (as part of cytochromes), and DNA synthesis (Abbaspour, Hurrell, & Kelishadi, 2014).
- **Mechanisms of Action:** Iron binds to oxygen in hemoglobin and myoglobin, facilitating oxygen transport and storage. In enzymes, iron acts as a cofactor in redox reactions (Abbaspour et al., 2014).

- Deficiency Effects: Anemia, fatigue, impaired cognitive function, weakened immune response (S. B. Kumar, Arnipalli, Mehta, Carrau, & Ziouzenkova, 2022).
- Excess Effects: Hemochromatosis (iron overload), liver damage, heart problems, diabetes (McDowell, Kudaravalli, Chen, & Sticco, 2024).

Zinc (Zn)

- Why Essential: Zinc is involved in numerous aspects of cellular metabolism, enzyme function, immune response, protein synthesis, DNA synthesis, and cell division (Wessels, Maywald, & Rink, 2017).
- Mechanisms of Action: Zinc is a cofactor for over 300 enzymes, stabilizes protein structures, and regulates gene expression (Cardini et al., 2021).
- Deficiency Effects: Growth retardation, delayed sexual maturation, impaired immune function, hair loss, diarrhea, eye and skin lesions (Hassan, Sada, Ketheeswaran, Dubey, & Bhat, 2020).
- Excess Effects: Nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, stomach cramps, diarrhea, and headaches; chronic excess can lead to copper deficiency (Agnew & Slesinger, 2022).

Copper (Cu)

- Why Essential: Copper is vital for iron metabolism, antioxidant defense, neuropeptide synthesis, connective tissue formation, and energy production (Gao & Zhang, 2023).
- Mechanisms of Action: Copper is a cofactor for enzymes (e.g., cytochrome c oxidase, ceruloplasmin, and superoxide dismutase; Ruiz, Libedinsky, & Elorza, 2021).
- Deficiency Effects: Anemia, neutropenia, bone abnormalities, impaired immune function, cardiovascular and neurological problems (National Research Council, 2000).
- Excess Effects: Wilson's disease (copper accumulation in tissues), liver damage, kidney failure, and neurological symptoms (Immergluck & Anilkumar, 2023).

Manganese (Mn)

- Why Essential: Manganese is vital for bone formation, amino acid metabolism, energy production, and antioxidant defenses (Horning, Caito, Tipps, Bowman, & Aschner, 2015).
- Mechanisms of Action: Manganese is a cofactor for enzymes like manganese superoxide dismutase, arginase, and pyruvate carboxylase (P. Chen, 2018).
- Deficiency Effects: Bone malformation, impaired growth, reproductive problems, glucose intolerance, and altered lipid metabolism (Institute of Medicine, 2001a).
- Excess Effects: Neurotoxicity, manganism (a Parkinson-like disease), liver damage, and impaired motor skills (Evans & Masullo, 2023).

Molybdenum (Mo)

- Why Essential: Molybdenum is a component of several enzymes necessary to metabolize sulfur-containing amino acids, purines, and pyrimidines (Sardesai, 1993).
- Mechanisms of Action: Molybdenum is a cofactor for enzymes (e.g., sulfite oxidase, xanthine oxidase, and aldehyde oxidase; Mendel, 2013).
- Deficiency Effects: Rare but can cause neurological problems, eye lens dislocation, and intellectual disability (Johannes, Fu, & Schwarz, 2022).
- Excess Effects: Relatively low toxicity; high levels can interfere with copper metabolism and cause symptoms similar to copper deficiency (Institute of Medicine, 2001b).

Cobalt (Co)

- **Why Essential:** Cobalt is part of vitamin B12 (cobalamin), essential for red blood cell production and neurological function (González-Montaña et al., 2020).
- **Mechanisms of Action:** Cobalt is a component of cobalamin, necessary for DNA synthesis and methylation (Al Amin & Gupta, 2023).
- **Deficiency Effects:** Anemia, fatigue, neurological disorders, cognitive decline (R. J. Chen & Lee, 2023).
- **Excess Effects:** Cardiomyopathy, hypothyroidism, and potential increased risk of cancer (R. J. Chen & Lee, 2023).

Chromium (Cr)

- **Why Essential:** Chromium is vital for macronutrient metabolism and enhances the action of insulin (Bertinato & Griffin, 2023).
- **Mechanisms of Action:** Chromium binds to chromodulin, potentiating insulin signaling (Hua, Clark, Ren, & Sreejayan, 2012).
- **Deficiency Effects:** Impaired glucose tolerance, weight loss, peripheral neuropathy, confusion (Bodman, Dreyer, & Varacallo, 2024).
- **Excess Effects:** Potential renal failure, liver damage, skin rashes, and lung cancer (primarily from industrial exposure to hexavalent chromium; Reif & Murray, 2024).

Essential heavy metals play critical roles in numerous biological processes. Deficiencies can lead to serious health issues (e.g., anemia, impaired cognitive function, and weakened immunity; Jaishankar, Tseten, Anbalagan, Mathew, & Beeregowda, 2014). Conversely, excess intake of these metals can also be harmful, causing conditions like hemochromatosis, neurotoxicity, and liver damage (Porter & Rawla, 2023). Maintaining a proper balance through diet and, if necessary, supplements is crucial for optimal health.

Environmentally Toxic Heavy Metals

Environmentally toxic heavy metals are prevalent in various natural and industrial sources. Human exposure to these metals can occur through inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. The adverse effects of these metals range from neurological damage and cognitive deficits to cancer, respiratory issues, and organ damage.

Lead (Pb)

Reservoirs and Sources:

- Natural deposits in the Earth's crust
- Industrial activities (e.g., mining, smelting, and manufacturing)
- Lead-based paints, gasoline, batteries, and plumbing materials

Routes of Exposure:

- Inhalation of lead dust or fumes
- Ingestion of lead-contaminated water, food, or soil
- Dermal contact with lead-containing products

Adverse Effects:

- Neurological damage, particularly in children, leading to cognitive deficits, behavioral issues, and reduced IQ (Sanders, Liu, Buchner, & Tchounwou, 2009)
- Kidney damage
- Hypertension and cardiovascular problems
- Reproductive toxicity and developmental delays

*Mercury (Hg)***Reservoirs and Sources:**

- Natural volcanic activity and geothermal processes
- Industrial emissions, coal combustion, gold mining, and manufacturing
- Release from broken thermometers, dental amalgams, and certain vaccines

Routes of Exposure:

- Inhalation of mercury vapors
- Ingestion of contaminated fish and seafood (methylmercury)
- Dermal absorption from mercury-containing products.

Adverse Effects:

- Neurotoxicity, leading to tremors, memory loss, and cognitive impairments (Paduraru et al., 2022)
- Damage to the kidneys and liver
- Developmental toxicity in fetuses, causing cerebral palsy and cognitive deficits
- Immune system suppression

*Cadmium (Cd)***Reservoirs and Sources:**

- Natural deposits in the Earth's crust
- Industrial processes (e.g., smelting, battery manufacturing, and plastic production)
- Contaminated food (e.g., leafy vegetables, grains) and tobacco smoke

Routes of Exposure:

- Inhalation of cadmium fumes or dust
- Ingestion of contaminated food and water
- Dermal contact with cadmium-containing products

Adverse Effects:

- Kidney damage and renal dysfunction
- Bone demineralization and increased risk of fractures (Itai-itai disease)
- Respiratory issues and lung cancer (Faroon et al., 2012)
- Reproductive toxicity and developmental delays

Arsenic (As)

Reservoirs and Sources:

- Natural deposits in the Earth's crust
- Industrial processes, including mining, smelting, and pesticide manufacturing
- Contaminated groundwater, especially in certain geographic regions (e.g., Bangladesh, India)

Routes of Exposure:

- Ingestion of contaminated water, food, or soil
- Inhalation of arsenic-containing dust or fumes
- Dermal contact with arsenic-treated wood or soil

Adverse Effects:

- Skin lesions and pigmentation changes (Dastgiri et al., 2010)
- Increased risk of cancers (skin, lung, bladder, kidney; Speer, Zhou, Volk, Liu, & Hudson, 2023)
- Cardiovascular diseases
- Neurological effects, including peripheral neuropathy and cognitive deficits

Chromium (Cr)

Reservoirs and Sources:

- Natural deposits in the Earth's crust
- Industrial processes (e.g., stainless steel production, leather tanning, and chromate manufacturing)
- Contaminated water from industrial discharge

Routes of Exposure:

- Inhalation of chromium dust or fumes
- Ingestion of contaminated water or food
- Dermal contact with chromium-containing products

Adverse Effects:

- Respiratory issues, including asthma and lung cancer (Wilbur et al., 2012)
- Skin irritation and ulcers
- Kidney and liver damage
- Genotoxicity and increased cancer risk

Nickel (Ni)

Reservoirs and Sources:

- Natural deposits in the Earth's crust
- Industrial processes (e.g., mining, smelting, and stainless steel manufacturing)

- Nickel-containing products (e.g., jewelry, batteries)

Routes of Exposure:

- Inhalation of nickel dust or fumes
- Ingestion of contaminated food and water
- Dermal contact with nickel-containing products

Adverse Effects:

- Respiratory issues, including asthma and lung cancer (Iskandar et al., 2024)
- Skin dermatitis (nickel allergy)
- Cardiovascular problems
- Potential carcinogenic effects

Understanding these toxic metals' sources, routes of exposure, and health impacts is crucial for developing effective prevention and mitigation strategies.

Discussion

Health Conditions, Disorders, and Diseases Caused by Environmentally Toxic Heavy Metal Exposure

Exposure to environmentally toxic heavy metals can lead to a wide range of health conditions, disorders, and diseases in humans. Each metal has specific health impacts, affecting various organs and systems and causing severe and sometimes irreversible damage (Table 1).

Table 1. Health Effects of Specific Heavy Metals

Heavy Metal	Health Effects
(Córdoba-Gamboa et al., 2023; Donzelli et al., 2019; Eastman & Tortora, 2022; Halmo & Nappe, 2023; S. Kumar, 2018; Rastogi, 2008; Ruebner, Hooper, Parrish, Furth, & Fadrowski, 2019; Tsoi, Lo, Cheung, & Cheung, 2021)	Neurological Disorders: Cognitive deficits and reduced IQ, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), encephalopathy, peripheral neuropathy
	Hematological Conditions: Anemia
	Renal Conditions: Chronic kidney disease
	Cardiovascular Diseases: Hypertension
	Reproductive Issues: Miscarriages and reduced fertility
	Developmental Delays: Stunted growth and developmental delays in children
(Bernhoft, 2012; Cao et al., 2010; Foley, Seidel, Sevier, Wendt, & Kogan, 2020; Posin, Kong, & Sharma, 2023)	Neurological Disorders: Tremors, memory loss, cognitive impairments, erethism, Minamata disease
	Renal Conditions: Nephrotic syndrome and renal failure
	Hepatic Conditions: Liver damage
	Developmental Issues: Cerebral palsy, cognitive deficits in fetuses and young children (prenatal exposure)
	Immunological Issues: Suppression of the immune system
(Gonzalez-Nahm et al., 2020; Rahimzadeh, Rahimzadeh,	Renal Conditions: Chronic kidney disease and renal dysfunction
	Bone Disorders: Itai-itai disease, osteomalacia, osteoporosis
	Respiratory Conditions: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), lung cancer
	Cardiovascular Issues: Hypertension and cardiovascular diseases

Kazemi, & Moghadamnia, 2017; Tsai et al., 2021)	Reproductive Issues: Reduced fertility and adverse pregnancy outcomes
Arsenic (As) (Shajil & Mahabal, 2023; States, Srivastava, Chen, & Barchowsky, 2009; Wei, Zhang, & Tao, 2019)	Dermatological Conditions: Hyperkeratosis, pigmentation changes, skin cancer
	Oncological Conditions: Lung, bladder, kidney cancers
	Cardiovascular Diseases: Hypertension and cardiovascular diseases
	Neurological Effects: Peripheral neuropathy, cognitive deficits
	Gastrointestinal Issues: Gastrointestinal irritation and liver damage
Chromium (Cr) (Xiao, Wu, Han, & Liu, 2023)	Respiratory Issues: Chronic respiratory conditions
	Respiratory Conditions: Asthma, bronchitis, lung cancer
	Dermatological Conditions: Contact dermatitis, skin ulcers
	Renal Conditions: Kidney damage
	Hepatic Conditions: Liver damage
Nickel (Ni) (Fischer et al., 2020; Kreyberg, 1978)	Oncological Conditions: Increased risk of various cancers, particularly lung cancer
	Genotoxic Effects: DNA damage and mutagenesis
	Respiratory Conditions: Asthma, chronic bronchitis, lung cancer
	Dermatological Conditions: Contact dermatitis (nickel allergy), eczema
	Cardiovascular Diseases: Hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases
	Oncological Conditions: Nasal cancer, lung cancer
	Renal Conditions: Kidney damage and renal dysfunction

Heavy Metals and Their Effects on the Placenta and Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes

Exposure to hazardous environmental toxins (e.g., lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel) poses significant risks to pregnant women and their developing fetuses. These heavy metals can cross the placental barrier, directly impacting fetal development and resulting in adverse pregnancy outcomes (Molina-Mesa et al., 2022). The placenta, acting as an organ interface between the mother and fetus, can be significantly affected by these metals—resulting in impaired nutrient and oxygen transport, oxidative stress, and inflammation (Ruano, Miralles, Méhats, & Vaiman, 2022).

Lead

Lead exposure during pregnancy is particularly concerning due to its ability to cross the placenta and accumulate in fetal tissues (Thomason et al., 2019). This exposure can result in neurodevelopmental toxicity, causing cognitive deficits, reduced IQ, and behavioral problems in children (Abelsohn & Sanborn, 2010). High levels of lead exposure are associated with increased risks of preterm birth, low birth weight, and miscarriage (Sahu et al., 2024). The developing nervous system is especially vulnerable to lead toxicity, which can cause long-term neurological and developmental issues.

Mercury

Mercury, especially in its methylmercury form, readily crosses the placenta and accumulates in fetal tissues, including the brain (Hong, Kim, & Lee, 2012). Prenatal mercury exposure is linked to severe neurodevelopmental outcomes (e.g., cerebral palsy, mental retardation, and motor dysfunction; Myers & Davidson, 1998). Even low levels of mercury exposure can impair cognitive development and lead to learning disabilities (N. B. Patel et al., 2019). The critical period of brain development makes the fetus highly susceptible to mercury's toxic effects, with potential consequences lasting throughout life.

Cadmium

Cadmium exposure during pregnancy can result in significant placental dysfunction (Hua Wang et al., 2016). This metal accumulates in the placenta, disrupting its normal functions and impairing nutrient and oxygen transport to the fetus (Jacobo-Estrada, Santoyo-Sánchez, Thévenod, & Barbier, 2017). Cadmium-induced placental damage is associated with restricted fetal growth, resulting in low birth weight and

intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR; Laine et al., 2015). Furthermore, cadmium exposure is linked to an increased risk of preeclampsia, a pregnancy complication characterized by high blood pressure and damage to other organ systems.

Arsenic

Arsenic exposure during pregnancy can have devastating effects on both the placenta and fetal development (Ortiz-Garcia et al., 2023). Arsenic crosses the placental barrier, resulting in fetal exposure and potential toxicity (Ortiz-Garcia et al., 2023). This exposure is associated with increased risks of stillbirth, neonatal mortality, and low birth weight. Chronic arsenic exposure can cause placental insufficiency, reducing the delivery of essential nutrients and oxygen to the fetus, and is linked to long-term health effects (e.g., impaired immune function and increased susceptibility to infections in the offspring).

Chromium

Hexavalent chromium (Cr VI) is particularly harmful during pregnancy due to its ability to cross the placenta and cause oxidative stress and DNA damage (Banu et al., 2017). Exposure to hexavalent chromium is associated with increased risks of miscarriage, preterm birth, and low birth weight. The oxidative damage induced by chromium can disrupt normal placental function and fetal development, resulting in adverse pregnancy outcomes (Banu et al., 2017). Chromium exposure may also affect the endocrine system, potentially interfering with hormonal regulation critical for pregnancy maintenance and fetal growth.

Nickel

Nickel exposure during pregnancy can lead to several adverse outcomes due to its placental transfer and accumulation in fetal tissues (Ding et al., 2021). High levels of nickel exposure are linked to an increased risk of spontaneous abortion, preterm birth, and low birth weight. Nickel can induce oxidative stress and inflammation in the placenta, disrupting its function and impairing fetal development (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, & Office on Smoking and Health, 2010). Additionally, nickel exposure is associated with an increased risk of congenital anomalies and developmental delays, affecting the long-term health and well-being of the offspring.

These disruptions in placental function can cause a range of adverse pregnancy outcomes, including preterm birth, low birth weight, IUGR, and increased risks of neurodevelopmental disorders and congenital anomalies in the offspring (Chew & Verma, 2023). Consequently, exposure to these environmental toxins during pregnancy can profoundly affect fetal development and long-term health (Rani & Dhok, 2023).

Heavy Metals Crossing the Placental Barrier

Environmentally toxic heavy metals (e.g., lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel) have the alarming ability to cross the placental barrier, a critical structure designed to protect the developing fetus (Molina-Mesa et al., 2022). On a cellular and functional level, this transfer involves complex interactions with placental cells and mechanisms that can compromise fetal health (Molina-Mesa et al., 2022).

Table 2 summarizes specific heavy metals' mechanism of placental crossing and its effects on placental function.

Table 2. Mechanisms of Heavy Metal Crossing the Placental Barrier and Their Effects

Heavy Metal	Mechanism of Placental Crossing	Effects on Placental Function
Lead	Crosses through passive diffusion and active transport, mimicking calcium to enter via calcium channels (Rísová, 2019).	Induces oxidative stress, disrupts mitochondrial activity, accumulates in placental tissue, impairs nutrient and oxygen transport
Mercury	Methylmercury crosses through passive diffusion and facilitated transport, forming complexes with amino acids. Elemental mercury vapor crosses and is oxidized (Bridges & Zalups, 2017).	Induces oxidative stress, disrupts mitochondrial function, causes cellular damage, and impairs nutrient transfer
Cadmium	Crosses primarily through active transport, competing with zinc and iron for transport proteins like DMT1 and zinc transporters (Jacobo-Estrada et al., 2017).	Induces oxidative stress, inflammation, apoptosis, impairs structural integrity and transport protein expression, compromises nutrient delivery
Arsenic	Crosses through passive diffusion and active transport, utilizing phosphate transporters (International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2012).	Interferes with cellular respiration, induces oxidative stress, compromises placental function, disrupts endocrine functions
Chromium	Crosses primarily through active transport, reduced to Cr III inside cells (Banu et al., 2017).	Causes oxidative stress, DNA damage, impairs nutrient and oxygen transport, generates ROS, induces apoptosis
Nickel	Crosses through passive diffusion and active transport, competing with iron and magnesium for transport pathways (Hou et al., 2011).	Induces oxidative stress, inflammation, cellular damage, interferes with nutrient and oxygen transport, disrupts endocrine functions

The ability of these heavy metals to cross the placental barrier involves intricate interactions with placental cells and transport mechanisms. By mimicking or competing with essential nutrients, these metals gain entry into placental cells, where they induce oxidative stress, disrupt mitochondrial function, and alter nutrient transport processes (Rodríguez-Cano, Calzada-Mendoza, Estrada-Gutierrez, Mendoza-Ortega, & Perichart-Perera, 2020). The resulting cellular and functional impairments in the placenta can lead to a range of adverse pregnancy outcomes, highlighting the critical need for strategies to reduce environmental exposure to these toxic heavy metals (Wai, Mar, Kosaka, Umemura, & Watanabe, 2017).

Overview of the Epigenetic Changes Caused by Environmentally Toxic Heavy Metal Exposure in Humans

Exposure to environmentally toxic heavy metals (e.g., lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel) can induce profound epigenetic changes in humans (Table 3; Ijomone et al., 2020). These changes alter gene expression without changing the DNA sequence (Al Aboud, Tupper, & Jialal, 2023). These changes can affect health and development, often spanning generations (Notterman & Mitchell, 2015).

Table 3. Effects of Heavy Metals on Epigenetic Pathways

Pathway	Description
DNA Methylation	Addition of a methyl group to cytosine residues in DNA, typically at CpG dinucleotides, generally suppressing gene expression. Heavy metals like arsenic and cadmium cause aberrant patterns, affecting tumor suppressor genes and oncogenes, provoking cancer. Lead exposure affects genes involved in neurological development (Kushwaha et al., 2016; Li et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2014).

Histone Modifications	Chemical modifications to histones influence gene expression by altering chromatin structure. Heavy metals can induce changes in histone acetylation, methylation, phosphorylation, and ubiquitination (e.g., nickel reduces histone acetylation, and cadmium disrupts DNA damage repair, provoking cancer; Genchi, Carocci, Lauria, Sinicropi, & Catalano, 2020; Genchi, Sinicropi, Lauria, Carocci, & Catalano, 2020; Mercadante & Kasi, 2023).
Non-Coding RNAs	Non-coding RNAs, including miRNAs and lncRNAs, regulate genes. Heavy metals alter their expression, dysregulating target genes. Mercury affects miRNAs involved in neuronal development, and arsenic alters lncRNAs, affecting pathways in cell proliferation and cancer (Islam, Zhao, Wang, Lu-Yao, & Liu, 2022; Ke et al., 2023).

Transgenerational Epigenetic Effects

One of the most concerning aspects of heavy metal-induced epigenetic changes is their potential to be transmitted across generations. Epigenetic modifications can be inherited, meaning that the effects of exposure to heavy metals can persist in the offspring of exposed individuals, even if the offspring themselves are not directly exposed (Bitto, Pizzino, Irrera, Galfo, & Squadrito, 2014). For example, studies have shown that prenatal exposure to lead can cause epigenetic changes that affect the health and development of multiple generations (Kundakovic & Jaric, 2017). These transgenerational effects highlight the long-lasting impact of environmental toxins on human health (Rebuzzini et al., 2022).

Health Implications

The epigenetic changes induced by heavy metal exposure can lead to a wide range of health issues. These include increased risks of cancer, neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and metabolic disorders (Stepanyan et al., 2023). These metals can disrupt essential biological processes by altering the normal gene expression patterns, contributing to chronic diseases and reduced life expectancy (Martinez-Zamudio & Ha, 2011). Furthermore, the ability of these changes to be inherited means that the health impacts of heavy metal exposure can affect not just individuals but entire populations over time (Jaishankar et al., 2014).

In summary, environmentally toxic heavy metals cause significant epigenetic changes that disrupt gene expression and contribute to various health issues (Martinez-Zamudio & Ha, 2011). These changes can be inherited, leading to lasting effects across generations (Nelson & Nadeau, 2010). Understanding the epigenetic mechanisms of heavy metal toxicity is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate their harmful impacts and protect public health (Jaishankar et al., 2014).

Possible Harmful Heavy Metals in Pharmaceuticals

Heavy metals can enter pharmaceuticals through various routes, posing significant health risks to consumers. These metals, which include lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel, can contaminate medications during manufacturing processes or through raw materials (Table 4). Their presence in pharmaceuticals is particularly concerning because patients often rely on these products for health and well-being, making the unintentional intake of toxic metals a critical issue (Tchounwou, Yedjou, Patlolla, & Sutton, 2012).

Table 4. Specific Heavy Metal Contamination in Pharmaceuticals

Heavy Metal	Pharmaceutical
Lead	Contamination can occur through raw materials, manufacturing processes, or packaging. Prolonged use medications like over-the-counter painkillers, dietary supplements, or herbal remedies can accumulate lead, causing severe health consequences (Mahdi et al., 2020).
Mercury	Historically used in pharmaceuticals as methylmercury or thimerosal (Institute of Medicine, 2001c).

Cadmium	Can contaminate pharmaceuticals through raw materials, particularly plant-based ones from cadmium-rich soils. Unintentional consumption of contaminated supplements or herbal products poses significant health risks, especially for those with kidney conditions (Koons & Rajasurya, 2023).
Arsenic	Contamination can happen via contaminated water or soil in the cultivation of plant-based raw materials. Poses significant health risks in medications, particularly in herbal and traditional medicines (Kuivenhoven & Mason, 2023).
Chromium	Hexavalent chromium (Cr VI) contamination occurs through industrial pollution and contaminated raw materials (Tumolo et al., 2020).
Nickel	Contamination can result from nickel-containing equipment during manufacturing or through raw materials (Genchi, Carocci, et al., 2020).

The contamination of pharmaceuticals with heavy metals poses a serious public health risk, given the widespread reliance on these products for health maintenance and disease treatment. Heavy metals can enter pharmaceuticals through various routes, including contaminated raw materials, inadequate manufacturing processes, and packaging materials (Mukhi, Rukmini, Ajay Manjrekar, Iyyaswami, & Sindhu, 2022). The health effects of these metals are diverse and severe, ranging from neurological damage and kidney failure to cancer and cardiovascular diseases (P. Chen, Miah, & Aschner, 2016). Ensuring the safety of pharmaceuticals requires rigorous quality control, stringent regulatory standards, and continuous monitoring to prevent contamination and protect public health.

Pharmaceuticals derived from plant-based raw materials

Table 5 illustrates several pharmaceuticals derived from plant-based raw materials and their sources and uses.

Table 5. Plant-Based Raw Material Pharmaceuticals, Sources, and Uses

Pharmaceutical	Source	Uses
Aspirin (Acetylsalicylic Acid)	Willow bark (<i>Salix</i> species)	Pain relief, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic (fever reducer), anticoagulant (blood thinner; Altinterim, 2013)
Morphine	Opium poppy (<i>Papaver somniferum</i>)	Pain relief, particularly for severe pain (Krashin, Trescot, & Murinova, 2013)
Digoxin	Foxglove plant (<i>Digitalis</i> species)	Treatment of various heart conditions, including atrial fibrillation and heart failure (David & Shetty, 2023)
Paclitaxel (Taxol)	Pacific yew tree (<i>Taxus brevifolia</i>)	Chemotherapy agent used to treat various cancers, including ovarian and breast cancer (Weaver, 2014)
Quinine	Cinchona tree bark (<i>Cinchona</i> species)	Treatment of malaria (Gachelin, Garner, Ferroni, Tröhler, & Chalmers, 2017)
Atropine	Belladonna plant (<i>Atropa belladonna</i>)	Treating bradycardia (slow heart rate), used as an antispasmodic, and dilating pupils during eye exams (Rajput, 2014)
Vincristine and Vinblastine	Madagascar periwinkle (<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>)	Chemotherapy agents used to treat various cancers, including leukemia and Hodgkin's lymphoma (Škubník, Pavlíčková, Ruml, & Rimpelová, 2021)
Reserpine	Indian snakeroot (<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>)	Treatment of high blood pressure and certain mental health disorders (Lobay, 2015)
Ephedrine	Ephedra plant (<i>Ephedra</i> species)	Treatment of asthma, nasal congestion, and as a stimulant (Renuka Gajanan Chawke et al., 2024)
Artemisinin	Sweet wormwood (<i>Artemisia annua</i>)	Treatment of malaria (Goel, 2023)

Possible Harmful Heavy Metals in Natural Remedies

Natural remedies—while offering therapeutic benefits—can inadvertently pose health risks due to contamination with heavy metals (Luo et al., 2021). These metals, including lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel, can find their way into herbal supplements, traditional medicines, and other natural remedies through various pathways, from soil contamination to improper processing and packaging practices (Briffa, Sinagra, & Blundell, 2020).

Contamination Pathways

Heavy metals can contaminate natural remedies through several pathways:

- **Soil Contamination:** Plants used in natural remedies may absorb heavy metals from contaminated soil or water, especially in areas with industrial pollution or mining activities (Priya, Muruganandam, Ali, & Kornaros, 2023).
- **Processing and Packaging:** Improper handling and storage practices during processing and packaging can introduce heavy metals from equipment or packaging materials into the products (Alamri et al., 2021).
- **Raw Material Quality:** Poor quality control of raw materials sourced from regions with lax environmental standards can lead to contamination (Rojas, Ruiz-Sánchez, Ríos, Ruiz-Chow, & Reséndiz-Albor, 2021).

Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP)

GMP guidelines are essential for ensuring the safety and quality of natural remedies:

- **Quality Control:** GMP requires rigorous quality control measures to ensure raw materials are sourced from reputable suppliers and tested for heavy metal contamination (Hongting Wang et al., 2023).
- **Facility Standards:** GMP mandates adherence to strict cleanliness and hygiene standards in manufacturing facilities to prevent cross-contamination and ensure product purity (Covarrubias, Rivera, Soto, Deeks, & Kalergis, 2022).
- **Documentation and Records:** GMP requires comprehensive documentation of manufacturing processes, including testing results for heavy metals, to ensure traceability and accountability (K. T. Patel & Chotai, 2011).
- **Training and Personnel:** GMP emphasizes training for personnel involved in manufacturing, handling, and packaging natural remedies to maintain high quality and safety standards (Gouveia, Rijo, Gonçalo, & Reis, 2015).

Regulatory Oversight

- **Effective regulatory oversight** is crucial for enforcing GMP guidelines and protecting consumers from contaminated natural remedies:
- **Testing Requirements:** Regulatory agencies may require routine testing of natural remedies for heavy metal contamination to ensure compliance with safety standards (Tracy, Guo, Liang, Bartram, & Fisher, 2020).
- **Labeling Requirements:** Clear labeling of heavy metal content and adherence to permissible limits are essential for informing consumers about potential risks (Alinezhad, Hashemi, & Tavakoly Sany, 2024).
- **Market Surveillance:** Regulatory agencies conduct market surveillance to monitor the safety and quality of natural remedies—taking enforcement actions against non-compliant products (Hamill, David-Barrett, Mwanga, Mshana, & Hampshire, 2021).

While natural remedies offer potential health benefits, their safety can be compromised by contamination with heavy metals. Heavy metals present in natural remedies pose significant health risks due to their toxicity and potential for long-term health effects (Tchounwou et al., 2012). Adherence to GMP and rigorous regulatory oversight are critical to ensuring the safety and quality of natural remedies, protecting consumers from harmful heavy metal exposure, and promoting public health (Hongting Wang et al., 2023).

Medical Process and Procedures for Diagnosing Toxic Heavy Metal Exposure in Humans

Diagnosing toxic heavy metal exposure in humans involves a comprehensive approach that integrates history-taking, physical examination, neuroimaging (if indicated), laboratory tests, neurological examination, motor function testing, electrophysiological studies, exclusion of other causes, and assessment of response to treatment (Rajkumar, Lee, & Gupta, 2023).

History and Physical Examination

- **History:** The physician begins by taking a detailed history, including occupational exposure, environmental exposure (e.g., living near industrial sites, using contaminated water sources), dietary habits (especially seafood consumption for mercury exposure), and potential exposure through hobbies or cultural practices (e.g., traditional medicines; Institute of Medicine, 1995).
- **Symptom Evaluation:** Symptoms associated with heavy metal exposure vary depending on the metal but may include neurological symptoms (e.g., cognitive deficits, tremors), gastrointestinal complaints, renal dysfunction, respiratory issues, dermatological symptoms, and systemic manifestations (e.g., fatigue and weight loss; P. Chen et al., 2016).
- **Physical Examination:** A thorough physical examination focuses on neurological signs (e.g., motor function, coordination, reflexes), dermatological changes, and signs of systemic toxicity (e.g., hypertension, signs of renal or liver dysfunction; Institute of Medicine, 1995).

Neuroimaging

Neuroimaging studies, e.g., magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) scans, may be indicated to evaluate structural changes in the brain or other affected organs, especially if neurological symptoms are present, or to assess for possible sources of metal deposition (e.g., brain MRI for mercury toxicity; Ramos, Oliveira, Sobrido, & Coppola, 2017).

Reasons or Indications for Neuroimaging in Suspected Toxic Heavy Metal Exposure

Neuroimaging (e.g., MRI or CT scans) may be indicated in suspected cases of toxic heavy metal exposure for several reasons:

- **Neurological Symptoms:** If the patient presents with neurological symptoms (e.g., cognitive deficits, tremors, ataxia, or seizures), neuroimaging can help identify structural abnormalities in the brain that may be associated with heavy metal toxicity (P. Chen et al., 2016).
- **Specific Metal Deposition:** Certain heavy metals can accumulate in particular brain regions (e.g., basal ganglia). Neuroimaging can detect these deposits, aiding in diagnosing and assessing the extent of metal deposition (P. Chen et al., 2016).
- **Evaluation of Encephalopathy:** Heavy metal poisoning can lead to encephalopathy, which may present with altered mental status, confusion, or behavioral changes. Neuroimaging helps rule out other causes of encephalopathy and assess for any structural brain abnormalities (Rajkumar et al., 2023).
- **Monitoring Disease Progression:** In chronic exposure cases, periodic neuroimaging may be necessary to monitor changes in brain structure or detect progressive neurological damage (Yen, Lin, & Chiang, 2023).

- **Exclusion of Other Pathologies:** Neuroimaging helps exclude other potential causes of neurological symptoms (e.g., tumors, vascular abnormalities, or infections), ensuring an accurate diagnosis of heavy metal toxicity (Patwa & Flora, 2020).
- **Baseline Assessment:** Establishing a baseline with neuroimaging can be crucial in cases of ongoing or potential future exposure to heavy metals—allowing for comparison in follow-up assessments to track changes over time (Bakulski et al., 2020).
- **Guiding Treatment Decisions:** Neuroimaging findings can guide treatment decisions (e.g., initiating chelation therapy or supportive care) based on the extent of brain involvement or severity of symptoms (Aderinto, Olatunji, Abdulbasit, & Edun, 2023).

Overall, neuroimaging plays a crucial role in the diagnostic evaluation of suspected toxic heavy metal exposure, particularly when neurological symptoms are present or when metal deposition in the brain is concerned. It helps provide valuable insights into the brain's structural integrity and aids in formulating appropriate management strategies for individuals affected by heavy metal exposure (Yen et al., 2023).

Laboratory Tests

- **Blood and Urine Tests:** These tests are essential for measuring heavy metal levels in the body:
- **Blood Tests:** Measure current exposure levels, e.g., blood lead levels (Fisher & Gupta, 2024)
- **Urine Tests:** Assess recent exposure and can indicate ongoing or recent exposure, e.g., urine arsenic levels (National Research Council, 1999)
- **Heavy Metal Panels:** Specialized tests may be ordered depending on suspected exposure, e.g., hair analysis for chronic exposure, bone lead measurement for cumulative exposure (Rajkumar et al., 2023)

Neurological Examination

- **Cognitive Assessment:** Testing cognitive function, memory, attention, and executive function to detect neurological deficits associated with heavy metal toxicity (Sasaki & Carpenter, 2022).
- **Motor Function Testing:** Assessing motor skills, coordination, and muscle strength to detect signs of neurological impairment (Shahrokhi & Asuncion, 2023).

Electrophysiological Studies

Electrophysiological tests, e.g., nerve conduction studies (NCSs) and electromyography (EMG), may be performed to assess peripheral nerve function and detect neuropathy associated with heavy metal exposure (Plaut & Weiss, 2022).

Exclusion of Other Causes

It is crucial to exclude other potential causes of symptoms and neurological deficits (e.g., infectious diseases, autoimmune disorders, and metabolic conditions) through appropriate investigations and clinical assessments (Arango, Shoenfeld, Cervera, & Anaya, 2013).

Response to Treatment

- **Chelation Therapy:** In cases of severe heavy metal poisoning, chelation therapy may be administered to enhance metal elimination from the body. Monitoring metal levels in blood or urine is essential to assess treatment efficacy (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).
- **Symptomatic Treatment:** Supportive therapies such as medications for neurological symptoms (e.g., antiepileptic drugs for seizures) or renal support may be provided depending on symptoms and organ involvement (Subbarao, Silverman, & Eapen, 2023).

- **Long-Term Monitoring:** Patients with heavy metal exposure may require long-term monitoring of symptoms, organ function, and metal levels to evaluate treatment response and prevent recurrence (Rajkumar et al., 2023).

Diagnosing toxic heavy metal exposure in humans involves a multifaceted approach, integrating clinical history, physical examination, laboratory tests, neuroimaging (if indicated), and specialized neurological assessments. Prompt identification and management are essential to mitigate the adverse health effects associated with heavy metal toxicity and improve patient outcomes.

Medical and Pharmacological Methods for Eliminating Toxic Heavy Metals from the Human Body

Eliminating toxic heavy metals from the human body typically involves medical and pharmacological methods to enhance their excretion or reduce their absorption (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).

Chelation Therapy

Chelation therapy involves administering chelating agents. These agents bind to heavy metals in the body, forming complexes more readily excreted in urine or feces (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).

Dimercaptosuccinic Acid (DMSA):

- **Mechanism:** DMSA is effective for lead, mercury, and arsenic poisoning. It chelates these metals and enhances their elimination via urine (Sears, 2013).
- **Administration:** Usually given orally.
- **Course:** Treatment duration varies based on the severity and type of metal toxicity (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).

Dimercaptopropane Sulfonate (DMPS):

- **Mechanism:** DMPS is effective for mercury, arsenic, and certain other metals. It promotes metal excretion primarily through urine (Dawn & Whited, 2023).
- **Administration:** Can be given orally or intravenously, depending on the severity of toxicity and patient condition.
- **Monitoring:** Close monitoring of kidney function and electrolyte levels is essential during DMPS therapy (Dawn & Whited, 2023).

Calcium Disodium Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA):

- **Mechanism:** EDTA binds to a variety of metals, including lead, cadmium, and mercury. It forms stable complexes that are excreted mainly via urine (George & Brady, 2023).
- **Administration:** Typically administered intravenously under medical supervision.
- **Considerations:** EDTA therapy requires careful monitoring of kidney function and electrolyte levels due to potential renal toxicity (George & Brady, 2023).

Pharmacological Enhancers of Metal Excretion

Certain medications can enhance the excretion of specific heavy metals from the body.

Penicillamine:

- **Indication:** Used for copper and lead poisoning (Mejias & Ramphul, 2023).
- **Mechanism:** Acts as a chelating agent and increases urinary excretion of metals (Mejias & Ramphul, 2023).

- Administration: Usually taken orally.

Succimer (DMSA):

- Indication: Primarily used for lead poisoning in children (National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases, 2012).
- Mechanism: Similar to DMSA, it chelates lead and enhances its elimination through urine (National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases, 2012).
- Administration: Oral administration.

Supportive Therapies

Supportive measures are essential during chelation therapy to manage symptoms and support overall health (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).

- Fluids and Electrolytes: Adequate hydration helps facilitate the excretion of chelated metals through urine. Electrolyte balance should be closely monitored, especially during intravenous chelation therapy (Flora & Pachauri, 2010).
- Nutritional Support: Ensuring adequate nutrition, particularly with antioxidants and essential minerals, helps mitigate oxidative stress and replenish depleted nutrients during heavy metal detoxification (Sears, 2013).

Other Considerations

- Individualized Treatment: Treatment approaches should be tailored based on the specific heavy metal involved, the severity of toxicity, and the patient's overall health status (Rajkumar et al., 2023).
- Monitoring: Regular monitoring of heavy metal levels in blood or urine is crucial to assess treatment efficacy and guide therapy duration or intensity adjustments (Rajkumar et al., 2023).
- Patient Education: Educating patients on potential sources of heavy metal exposure and preventive measures are essential to prevent re-exposure after detoxification (Rajkumar et al., 2023).

The medical and pharmacological methods for eliminating toxic heavy metals from the human body primarily involve chelation therapy with agents like DMSA, DMPS, and EDTA, supported by pharmacological enhancers of metal excretion and comprehensive supportive care. Treatment should be managed by healthcare professionals experienced in toxicology and heavy metal poisoning to ensure safety and efficacy.

Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) Methods and Natural Remedies for Eliminating Toxic Heavy Metals from the Human Body

CAM approaches and natural remedies for eliminating toxic heavy metals from the human body are often considered adjuncts or alternatives to conventional medical treatments. These methods generally aim to support detoxification processes and enhance overall health. It is important to note that while some CAM approaches may have anecdotal support or traditional use, scientific evidence for their effectiveness and safety in heavy metal detoxification varies (Cassileth & Vickers, 2003).

Chlorella

Chlorella, a type of freshwater algae, is believed to bind to heavy metals and facilitate their elimination from the body. It is rich in chlorophyll and other nutrients that may support detoxification processes.

- Administration: Usually taken as a tablet or powder supplement.

- Mechanism: Chlorella's high chlorophyll content is thought to aid in detoxification by binding to heavy metals in the gastrointestinal tract and facilitating their excretion through feces (Kim, Kwon, & Kim, 2009).
- Considerations: Quality and purity of chlorella supplements vary; therefore, sourcing from reputable manufacturers is crucial.

Cilantro (Coriandrum sativum)

Cilantro, commonly used in culinary dishes, is purported to chelate heavy metals and aid in their elimination from the body.

- Administration: Consumed fresh as an herb or taken as a supplement.
- Mechanism: Contains compounds that may bind to heavy metals and promote their excretion through urine and feces (Mustafa, 2021).
- Considerations: Some individuals may be sensitive to cilantro, and excessive consumption can lead to digestive upset in some cases.

Spirulina

Spirulina, a type of blue-green algae, is often promoted for its detoxification properties, including the potential to remove heavy metals.

- Administration: Available as a dietary supplement in powder or tablet form.
- Mechanism: Contains proteins and peptides that may bind to heavy metals in the body and aid in their elimination through urine and feces (Al-Dhabi, 2013).
- Considerations: Quality and sourcing are essential due to potential contamination issues in algae-based supplements.

Garlic (Allium sativum)

Garlic is known for its antioxidant and detoxifying properties and has been suggested to support heavy metal detoxification.

- Administration: Consumed fresh or as a supplement.
- Mechanism: Contains sulfur compounds that may help chelate heavy metals and support liver detoxification processes (Sharma, Sharma, & Kansal, 2010).
- Considerations: Garlic supplements should be used cautiously, especially in high doses, as they may interact with medications and affect blood clotting.

Alpha-Lipoic Acid (ALA)

ALA is an antioxidant that has been studied for its potential to chelate heavy metals and protect against oxidative stress associated with metal toxicity.

- Administration: Available as a dietary supplement.
- Mechanism: ALA can bind to certain heavy metals and facilitate their removal from the body through urine (Nguyen, Pellegrini, & Gupta, 2024).
- Considerations: Dosage and duration of use should be guided by healthcare professionals, as ALA may interact with medications and affect blood sugar levels.

Activated Charcoal

Activated charcoal is known for its ability to bind to toxins, including heavy metals, in the gastrointestinal tract and facilitate their excretion.

- Administration: Taken orally as a powder or capsule.
- Mechanism: Adsorbs heavy metals and other toxins, preventing their absorption and facilitating elimination through feces (Silberman, Galuska, & Taylor, 2023).
- Considerations: Activated charcoal should be used under guidance, as it may interfere with the absorption of medications and nutrients.

Modified Citrus Pectin

Modified citrus pectin is a soluble fiber derived from citrus fruits that has been studied for its potential to chelate heavy metals and promote their excretion.

- Administration: Typically taken as a dietary supplement.
- Mechanism: Binds to heavy metals in the digestive tract and facilitates their elimination through feces (Lara-Espinoza, Carvajal-Millán, Balandrán-Quintana, López-Franco, & Rascón-Chu, 2018).
- Considerations: The supplement's quality and purity are important; however, evidence supporting its effectiveness in heavy metal detoxification is limited.

Considerations and Precautions

- Consultation: It is crucial to consult with a healthcare provider knowledgeable about heavy metal toxicity and integrative medicine before starting any CAM methods or natural remedies (Rajkumar et al., 2023).
- Monitoring: Regular monitoring of heavy metal levels and overall health status is important during detoxification processes (Rajkumar et al., 2023).
- Safety: Some natural remedies may have side effects or interactions with medications, highlighting the importance of informed and supervised use (Dores et al., 2023).

While CAM methods and natural remedies may offer potential benefits in heavy metal detoxification, their effectiveness and safety should be evaluated based on individual circumstances and in conjunction with conventional medical approaches when necessary.

Toxic Heavy Metals in Medical Tests, Procedures, and Imaging

Heavy metal use in medical diagnostics and therapeutic procedures is widespread due to their unique properties. However, exposure to these metals can pose significant health risks if not properly managed (Jaishankar et al., 2014).

Sources and Uses of Heavy Metals in Medical Contexts

Radiographic Contrast Agents:

- Barium: Used in barium swallow tests to enhance imaging of the gastrointestinal tract. Barium sulfate is generally safe, but soluble barium compounds are highly toxic (Moffett et al., 2007).
- Iodine: Used in various radiographic contrast agents (e.g., CT scans) to improve the visibility of blood vessels and tissues. While iodine is not a heavy metal, contrast agents can contain heavy metals as stabilizers or contaminants (Kaller & An, 2023).

MRI Contrast Agents:

- **Gadolinium:** Used as a contrast agent in MRI scans to enhance image quality. Gadolinium-based contrast agents (GBCAs) are typically safe, but gadolinium can lead to nephrogenic systemic fibrosis (NSF) in patients with impaired renal function (Cheong, Wilson, Preventza, & Muthupillai, 2022).

Radioisotopes in Nuclear Medicine:

- **Technetium-99m:** Widely used in diagnostic imaging, e.g., single-photon emission computerized tomography (SPECT) scans, due to its ideal physical properties. Although technetium is not a heavy metal, contamination with other heavy metals can occur during production (Kane, Padda, Patel, & Davis, 2024).
- **Thallium-201:** Used in myocardial perfusion imaging to assess blood flow to the heart. Thallium is highly toxic and can cause significant health effects if not handled properly (Poudyal, Shrestha, & Chowdhury, 2023).

Therapeutic Use of Heavy Metals:

- **Platinum-Based Chemotherapy:** Certain drugs (e.g., cisplatin, carboplatin, and oxaliplatin) are used in cancer treatment. These compounds can cause nephrotoxicity, neurotoxicity, and ototoxicity (Zhang, Xu, Gao, & Yao, 2022).
- **Gold Compounds:** Used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. Long-term use can lead to chrysiasis (skin discoloration) and organ toxicity (Balfourier, Kolosnjaj-Tabi, Luciani, Carn, & Gazeau, 2020).

Mechanisms of Action and Routes of Exposure

- **Ingestion and Absorption:** Oral contrast agents can cause exposure through ingestion. Although most are designed to be inert and non-absorbable, improper formulation or administration can result in the absorption of toxic compounds (Kaller & An, 2023).
- **Intravenous Administration:** Contrast agents and chemotherapeutic drugs administered intravenously can introduce heavy metals directly into the bloodstream, resulting in systemic exposure (Kaller & An, 2023).
- **Inhalation:** Radioactive aerosols used in specific nuclear medicine tests can be inhaled, posing a risk of internal contamination (Keith, Murray, & Spoo, 1999).
- **Dermal Exposure:** Handling heavy metals in medical settings can result in skin exposure, especially if proper protective measures are not followed (Anderson & Meade, 2014).

Health Effects of Heavy Metal Exposure from Medical Sources

Gadolinium:

- **Nephrogenic Systemic Fibrosis (NSF):** A debilitating condition characterized by fibrosis of the skin, joints, and internal organs, primarily in patients with renal impairment.
- **Gadolinium Deposition Disease (GDD):** Symptoms include persistent pain, cognitive disturbances, and skin thickening, although the condition is not well understood and controversial (Semelka & Ramalho, 2023).

Platinum Compounds:

- **Nephrotoxicity:** Cisplatin can cause significant kidney damage, requiring dose adjustments and hydration protocols to mitigate risks.
- **Neurotoxicity:** Peripheral neuropathy is a common side effect, particularly with prolonged use.

- Ototoxicity: Hearing loss can occur, particularly in younger patients (Sherief et al., 2022).

Thallium:

- Cardiotoxicity: Can affect the cardiovascular system, resulting in arrhythmias and myocardial damage.
- Neurotoxicity: Causes peripheral neuropathy, cognitive deficits, and ataxia (Peters & Staff, 2022).

Technetium-99m:

- Radiation Exposure: While generally considered safe due to its short half-life, improper handling can lead to unnecessary radiation exposure.
- Contaminant Metals: Potential exposure to other heavy metals used in production can have various toxic effects (Todd et al., 2020).

Gold Compounds:

- Chrysiasis: Discoloration of the skin due to gold deposition.
- Renal and Hepatic Toxicity: Long-term use can damage the kidneys and liver (Ahmed et al., 2018).

Preventive Measures and Safety Protocols

- Regulation and Quality Control: Ensuring strict regulatory standards and quality control during the production and administration of medical products containing heavy metals (Institute of Medicine, 2012).
- Patient Screening: Assessing risk factors (e.g., renal function) before administering potentially toxic agents (J. B. Patel & Sapra, 2023).
- Hydration Protocols: Hydration protocols can help mitigate renal damage from nephrotoxic agents like cisplatin (Crona et al., 2017).
- Protective Equipment and Procedures: Using appropriate protective measures to minimize exposure risk for healthcare workers handling these substances (Kening & Groen, 2023).

While heavy metals play an essential role in various medical diagnostics and treatments, their potential for toxicity requires careful management.

Conclusion

The pervasive presence of environmentally toxic heavy metals such as lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel has profound implications for human health due to their ability to induce significant epigenetic changes. Even at low exposure levels, these metals can alter gene expression without changing the DNA sequence, leading to health issues that can persist across generations. This transgenerational impact means that the consequences of exposure are not limited to the directly affected individual but can extend to their descendants, affecting health and development in myriad ways. Heavy metals interfere with critical biological processes through DNA methylation, histone modifications, and the alteration of non-coding RNA expressions. Lead exposure disrupts neurological development genes, while arsenic and cadmium induce aberrant DNA methylation patterns affecting oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes. These disruptions can lead to increased cancer risk, neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and metabolic syndromes, highlighting the extensive and varied health impacts of these toxic substances. These health impacts are exacerbated by heavy metals crossing the placental barrier, exposing fetuses to risks that can impair development and health from the earliest stages of life. Mechanisms of placental crossing include passive diffusion,

facilitated transport, and active transport, depending on the metal. These interactions can induce oxidative stress, disrupt mitochondrial functions, and impair nutrient and oxygen transport. The resulting damage stresses the need for stringent measures to limit environmental exposure to these metals. In addition to environmental exposure, the contamination of pharmaceuticals with heavy metals presents a significant public health risk. Medications, often contaminated during manufacturing or through raw materials, can inadvertently introduce toxic metals to patients, compounding the health risks. Rigorous quality control and stringent regulatory standards are essential to prevent such contamination and ensure the safety of pharmaceuticals.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that this paper was written without any commercial or financial relationship that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

- Abbaspour, N., Hurrell, R., & Kelishadi, R. (2014). Review on iron and its importance for human health. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences : The Official Journal of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences*, 19(2), 164–174.
- Abelsohn, A. R., & Sanborn, M. (2010). Lead and children: clinical management for family physicians. *Canadian Family Physician Medecin de Famille Canadien*, 56(6), 531–535.
- Aderinto, N., Olatunji, D., Abdulbasit, M., & Edun, M. (2023). The essential role of neuroimaging in diagnosing and managing cerebrovascular disease in Africa: a review. *Annals of Medicine*, 55(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/07853890.2023.2251490>
- Agnew, U. M., & Slesinger, T. L. (2022). Zinc Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Ahmed, A., Alkhawajah, A. M. M., Al-Tamimi, D. M., Shawarby, M. A., Isab, A. A., & Badar, A. (2018). Biological alterations in renal and hepatic tissues by a novel gold (III) anti-cancerous compound. *Iranian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences*, 21(10), 1064–1072. <https://doi.org/10.22038/IJBMS.2018.28622.6935>
- Al Aboud, N. M., Tupper, C., & Jialal, I. (2023). Genetics, Epigenetic Mechanism. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Al Amin, A. S. M., & Gupta, V. (2023). Vitamin B12 (Cobalamin). In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Alamri, M. S., Qasem, A. A. A., Mohamed, A. A., Hussain, S., Ibraheem, M. A., Shamlan, G., ... Qasha, A. S. (2021). Food packaging's materials: A food safety perspective. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28(8), 4490–4499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.04.047>
- Al-Dhabi, N. A. (2013). Heavy metal analysis in commercial Spirulina products for human consumption. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 20(4), 383–388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2013.04.006>
- Alinezhad, Z., Hashemi, M., & Tavakoly Sany, S. B. (2024). Concentration of heavy metals in pasteurized and sterilized milk and health risk assessment across the globe: A systematic review. *PLOS ONE*, 19(2), e0296649. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0296649>
- Altinterim, B. (2013). Effects of Willow Bark (*Salix alba*) and Its Salicylates on Blood Coagulant. *Karaelmas Science and Engineering Journal*, 3(1), 37–39.

- Anderson, S. E., & Meade, B. J. (2014). Potential Health Effects Associated with Dermal Exposure to Occupational Chemicals. *Environmental Health Insights*, 8(1), EHLS15258. <https://doi.org/10.4137/EHLS15258>
- Arango, M.-T., Shoenfeld, Y., Cervera, R., & Anaya, J.-M. (2013). Chapter 19 Infection and autoimmune diseases. In J.-M. Anaya, Y. Shoenfeld, A. Rojas-Villarraga, R. A. Levy, & R. Cervera (Eds.), *Autoimmunity: From Bench to Bedside*. Bogota, Colombia: El Rosario University Press.
- Bakulski, K. M., Seo, Y. A., Hickman, R. C., Brandt, D., Vadari, H. S., Hu, H., & Park, S. K. (2020). Heavy Metals Exposure and Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 76(4), 1215–1242. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-200282>
- Balfourier, A., Kolosnjaj-Tabi, J., Luciani, N., Carn, F., & Gazeau, F. (2020). Gold-based therapy: From past to present. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(37), 22639–22648. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2007285117>
- Banu, S. K., Stanley, J. A., Sivakumar, K. K., Arosh, J. A., Taylor, R. J., & Burghardt, R. C. (2017). Chromium VI – Induced developmental toxicity of placenta is mediated through spatiotemporal dysregulation of cell survival and apoptotic proteins. *Reproductive Toxicology*, 68, 171–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2016.07.006>
- Bernhoft, R. A. (2012). Mercury Toxicity and Treatment: A Review of the Literature. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2012, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/460508>
- Bertinato, J., & Griffin, P. (2023). A low chromium diet increases body fat, energy intake and circulating triglycerides and insulin in male and female rats fed a moderately high-fat, high-sucrose diet from peripuberty to young adult age. *PLOS ONE*, 18(1), e0281019. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281019>
- Bitto, A., Pizzino, G., Irrera, N., Galfo, F., & Squadrito, F. (2014). Epigenetic Modifications Due to Heavy Metals Exposure in Children Living in Polluted Areas. *Current Genomics*, 15(6), 464–468. <https://doi.org/10.2174/138920291506150106153336>
- Bodman, M. A., Dreyer, M. A., & Varacallo, M. (2024). Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Bridges, C. C., & Zalups, R. K. (2017). Mechanisms involved in the transport of mercuric ions in target tissues. *Archives of Toxicology*, 91(1), 63–81. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-016-1803-y>
- Briffa, J., Sinagra, E., & Blundell, R. (2020). Heavy metal pollution in the environment and their toxicological effects on humans. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04691>
- Cao, Y., Chen, A., Jones, R. L., Radcliffe, J., Caldwell, K. L., Dietrich, K. N., & Rogan, W. J. (2010). Does background postnatal methyl mercury exposure in toddlers affect cognition and behavior? *NeuroToxicology*, 31(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2009.10.017>
- Cardini, A., Pellegrino, E., White, P. J., Mazzolai, B., Mascherpa, M. C., & Ercoli, L. (2021). Transcriptional Regulation of Genes Involved in Zinc Uptake, Sequestration and Redistribution Following Foliar Zinc Application to *Medicago sativa*. *Plants*, 10(3), 476. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10030476>
- Cassileth, B. R., & Vickers, A. (2003). CAM Therapies and Practitioners. In D. W. Kufe, R. E. Pollock, R. R. Weichselbaum, R. C., Jr. Bast, T. S. Gansler, J. F. Holland, & E. III. Frei (Eds.), *Holland-Frei Cancer Medicine* (6th ed.). Hamilton, O.N.: BC Decker.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, & Office on Smoking and Health. (2010). 8 Reproductive and Developmental Effects. In

How Tobacco Smoke Causes Disease: The Biology and Behavioral Basis for Smoking-Attributable Disease: A Report of the Surgeon General. Atlanta, G.A.: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

Chen, P. (2018). Manganese metabolism in humans. *Frontiers in Bioscience*, 23(9), 4665. <https://doi.org/10.2741/4665>

Chen, P., Miah, M. R., & Aschner, M. (2016). Metals and Neurodegeneration. *F1000Research*, 5, 366. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.7431.1>

Chen, R. J., & Lee, V. R. (2023). Cobalt Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

Cheong, B. Y. C., Wilson, J. M., Preventza, O. A., & Muthupillai, R. (2022). Gadolinium-Based Contrast Agents: Updates and Answers to Typical Questions Regarding Gadolinium Use. *Texas Heart Institute Journal*, 49(3). <https://doi.org/10.14503/THIJ-21-7680>

Chew, L. C., & Verma, R. P. (2023). Fetal Growth Restriction. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

Córdoba-Gamboa, L., Vázquez-Salas, R. A., Romero-Martínez, M., Cantoral, A., Riojas-Rodríguez, H., Bautista-Arredondo, S., ... Téllez-Rojo, M. M. (2023). Lead Exposure Can Affect Early Childhood Development and Could Be Aggravated by Stunted Growth: Perspectives from Mexico. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 5174. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20065174>

Covarrubias, C. E., Rivera, T. A., Soto, C. A., Deeks, T., & Kalergis, A. M. (2022). Current GMP standards for the production of vaccines and antibodies: An overview. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.1021905>

Crona, D. J., Faso, A., Nishijima, T. F., McGraw, K. A., Galsky, M. D., & Milowsky, M. I. (2017). A Systematic Review of Strategies to Prevent Cisplatin-Induced Nephrotoxicity. *The Oncologist*, 22(5), 609–619. <https://doi.org/10.1634/theoncologist.2016-0319>

Dastgiri, S., Mosafieri, M., Fizi, M. A., Olfati, N., Zolali, S., Pouladi, N., & Azarfam, P. (2010). Arsenic Exposure, Dermatological Lesions, Hypertension, and Chromosomal Abnormalities among People in a Rural Community of Northwest Iran. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.3329/jhpn.v28i1.4519>

David, M. N. V., & Shetty, M. (2023). Digoxin. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

Dawn, L., & Whited, L. (2023). Dimercaprol. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

Ding, A.-L., Hu, H., Xu, F.-P., Liu, L.-Y., Peng, J., & Dong, X.-D. (2021). Pregnancy complications effect on the nickel content in maternal blood, placenta blood and umbilical cord blood during pregnancy. *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 9(28), 8340–8348. <https://doi.org/10.12998/wjcc.v9.i28.8340>

Donzelli, G., Carducci, A., Llopis-Gonzalez, A., Verani, M., Llopis-Morales, A., Cioni, L., & Morales-Suárez-Varela, M. (2019). The Association between Lead and Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(3), 382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16030382>

Dores, A. R., Peixoto, M., Castro, M., Sá, C., Carvalho, I. P., Martins, A., ... Marques, A. (2023). Knowledge and Beliefs about Herb/Supplement Consumption and Herb/Supplement–Drug Interactions among the General Population, including Healthcare Professionals and Pharmacists: A Systematic Review and Guidelines for a Smart Decision System. *Nutrients*, 15(10), 2298. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15102298>

Eastman, K. L., & Tortora, L. E. (2022). Lead Encephalopathy. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

- Evans, G. R., & Masullo, L. N. (2023). Manganese Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Faroon, O., Ashizawa, A., Wright, S., Tucker, P., Jenkins, K., Ingerman, L., & Rudisill, C. (2012). 3 HEALTH EFFECTS. In *Toxicological Profile for Cadmium*. Atlanta, G.A.: Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry.
- Fischer, R. S. B., Unrine, J. M., Vangala, C., Sanderson, W. T., Mandayam, S., & Murray, K. O. (2020). Evidence of nickel and other trace elements and their relationship to clinical findings in acute Mesoamerican Nephropathy: A case-control analysis. *PLOS ONE*, *15*(11), e0240988. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0240988>
- Fisher, R. M., & Gupta, V. (2024). Heavy Metals. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Flora, S. J. S., & Pachauri, V. (2010). Chelation in Metal Intoxication. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *7*(7), 2745–2788. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph7072745>
- Foley, M. M., Seidel, I., Sevier, J., Wendt, J., & Kogan, M. (2020). One man's swordfish story: The link between Alzheimer's disease and mercury exposure. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, *52*, 102499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2020.102499>
- Gachelin, G., Garner, P., Ferroni, E., Tröhler, U., & Chalmers, I. (2017). Evaluating Cinchona bark and quinine for treating and preventing malaria. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, *110*(1), 31–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076816681421>
- Gao, L., & Zhang, A. (2023). Copper-instigated modulatory cell mortality mechanisms and progress in oncological treatment investigations. *Frontiers in Immunology*, *14*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1236063>
- Genchi, G., Carocci, A., Lauria, G., Sinicropi, M. S., & Catalano, A. (2020). Nickel: Human Health and Environmental Toxicology. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(3), 679. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17030679>
- Genchi, G., Sinicropi, M. S., Lauria, G., Carocci, A., & Catalano, A. (2020). The Effects of Cadmium Toxicity. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(11), 3782. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17113782>
- George, T., & Brady, M. F. (2023). Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA). In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Goel, R. (2023). Current Antimalarial Treatments: Focus on Artemisia annua Dry Leaf. In P. P. Piccaluga (Ed.), *Malaria - Recent Advances and New Perspectives*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.106736>
- González-Montaña, J.-R., Escalera-Valente, F., Alonso, A. J., Lomillos, J. M., Robles, R., & Alonso, M. E. (2020). Relationship between Vitamin B12 and Cobalt Metabolism in Domestic Ruminant: An Update. *Animals*, *10*(10), 1855. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10101855>
- Gonzalez-Nahm, S., Nihlani, K., S. House, J., L. Maguire, R., G. Skinner, H., & Hoyo, C. (2020). Associations between Maternal Cadmium Exposure with Risk of Preterm Birth and Low Birth Weight: Effect of Mediterranean Diet Adherence on Affected Prenatal Outcomes. *Toxics*, *8*(4), 90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics8040090>
- Gouveia, B. G., Rijo, P., Gonçalo, T. S., & Reis, C. P. (2015). Good manufacturing practices for medicinal products for human use. *Journal of Pharmacy And Bioallied Sciences*, *7*(2), 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-7406.154424>
- Halmo, L., & Nappe, T. M. (2023). Lead Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

- Hamill, H., David-Barrett, E., Mwanga, J. R., Mshana, G., & Hampshire, K. (2021). Monitoring, reporting and regulating medicine quality: tensions between theory and practice in Tanzania. *BMJ Global Health*, 6(Suppl 3), e003043. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-003043>
- Hassan, A., Sada, K.-K., Ketheeswaran, S., Dubey, A. K., & Bhat, M. S. (2020). Role of Zinc in Mucosal Health and Disease: A Review of Physiological, Biochemical, and Molecular Processes. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.8197>
- Hong, Y.-S., Kim, Y.-M., & Lee, K.-E. (2012). Methylmercury Exposure and Health Effects. *Journal of Preventive Medicine & Public Health*, 45(6), 353–363. <https://doi.org/10.3961/jpmp.2012.45.6.353>
- Horning, K. J., Caito, S. W., Tipps, K. G., Bowman, A. B., & Aschner, M. (2015). Manganese Is Essential for Neuronal Health. *Annual Review of Nutrition*, 35(1), 71–108. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-nutr-071714-034419>
- Hou, Y.-P., Gu, J.-Y., Shao, Y.-F., Song, Y.-F., Jing, Y.-H., Wu, W.-S., & Pu, S. (2011). The characteristics of placental transfer and tissue concentrations of nickel in late gestational rats and fetuses. *Placenta*, 32(3), 277–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.placenta.2010.12.021>
- Hua, Y., Clark, S., Ren, J., & Sreejayan, N. (2012). Molecular mechanisms of chromium in alleviating insulin resistance. *The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 23(4), 313–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnutbio.2011.11.001>
- Ijomone, O. M., Ijomone, O. K., Iroegbu, J. D., Ifenatuoha, C. W., Olung, N. F., & Aschner, M. (2020). Epigenetic influence of environmentally neurotoxic metals. *NeuroToxicology*, 81, 51–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2020.08.005>
- Immergluck, J., & Anilkumar, A. C. (2023). Wilson Disease. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Institute of Medicine. (1995). A: Taking an Exposure History. In A. M. Pope & D. P. Rall (Eds.), *Environmental Medicine: Integrating a Missing Element into Medical Education*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/4795>
- Institute of Medicine. (2001a). 10 Manganese. In *Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin A, Vitamin K, Arsenic, Boron, Chromium, Copper, Iodine, Iron, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Silicon, Vanadium, and Zinc*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/10026>
- Institute of Medicine. (2001b). 11 Molybdenum. In *Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin A, Vitamin K, Arsenic, Boron, Chromium, Copper, Iodine, Iron, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Silicon, Vanadium, and Zinc*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/10026>
- Institute of Medicine. (2001c). Under Review: Thimerosal-Containing Vaccines and Neurodevelopmental Disorders. In K. Stratton, A. Gable, & M. C. McCormick (Eds.), *Immunization Safety Review: Thimerosal-Containing Vaccines and Neurodevelopmental Disorders*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/10208>
- Institute of Medicine. (2012). 3 Critical Issues. In J. E. Riviere & G. J. Buckley (Eds.), *Ensuring Safe Foods and Medical Products Through Stronger Regulatory Systems Abroad*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/13296>
- International Agency for Research on Cancer. (2012). Arsenic and Arsenic Compounds. In *Arsenic, Metals, Fibres and Dusts; IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans* (Vol. 100C). IARC Publications.
- Iskandar, I. Y. K., Gawkrödger, D. J., Byrne, L., Gittins, M., Carder, M., Fishwick, D., & van Tongeren, M. (2024). Trends in work-related respiratory diseases attributed to nickel, chromium and cobalt in the

- UK: descriptive findings from The Health and Occupation Research (THOR) network 1996–2019. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 81(4), 220–224. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2023-109066>
- Islam, R., Zhao, L., Wang, Y., Lu-Yao, G., & Liu, L.-Z. (2022). Epigenetic Dysregulations in Arsenic-Induced Carcinogenesis. *Cancers*, 14(18), 4502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14184502>
- Jacobo-Estrada, T., Santoyo-Sánchez, M., Thévenod, F., & Barbier, O. (2017). Cadmium Handling, Toxicity and Molecular Targets Involved during Pregnancy: Lessons from Experimental Models. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 18(7), 1590. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms18071590>
- Jaishankar, M., Tseten, T., Anbalagan, N., Mathew, B. B., & Beeregowda, K. N. (2014). Toxicity, mechanism and health effects of some heavy metals. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology*, 7(2), 60–72. <https://doi.org/10.2478/intox-2014-0009>
- Johannes, L., Fu, C.-Y., & Schwarz, G. (2022). Molybdenum Cofactor Deficiency in Humans. *Molecules*, 27(20), 6896. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27206896>
- Kaller, M. O., & An, J. (2023). Contrast Agent Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Kane, S. M., Padda, I. S., Patel, P., & Davis, D. D. (2024). Technetium-99m. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Ke, T., Tinkov, A., Skalny, A., Santamaria, A., Rocha, J., Bowman, A., ... Aschner, M. (2023). Epigenetics and Methylmercury-Induced Neurotoxicity, Evidence from Experimental Studies. *Toxics*, 11(1), 72. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics11010072>
- Keith, S., Murray, H. E., & Spoo, W. (1999). 6 SOURCES OF POPULATION EXPOSURE TO IONIZING RADIATION. In *Toxicological Profile for Ionizing Radiation*. Atlanta, G.A.: Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry.
- Kening, M. Z., & Groen, K. (2023). Personal Protective Equipment. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Kim, Y. J., Kwon, S., & Kim, M. K. (2009). Effect of *Chlorella vulgaris* intake on cadmium detoxification in rats fed cadmium. *Nutrition Research and Practice*, 3(2), 89. <https://doi.org/10.4162/nrp.2009.3.2.89>
- Koons, A. L., & Rajasurya, V. (2023). Cadmium Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Krashin, D., Trescot, A., & Murinova, N. (2013). Opioids and Pain Treatment. In K. Ramawat & J. M. Mérillon (Eds.), *Natural Products* (pp. 1367–1382). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22144-6_45
- Kreyberg, L. (1978). Lung cancer in workers in a nickel refinery. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 35(2), 109–116. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.35.2.109>
- Kuivenhoven, M., & Mason, K. (2023). Arsenic Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Kumar, S. (2018). Occupational and environmental exposure to lead and reproductive health impairment: An overview. *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 22(3), 128. https://doi.org/10.4103/ij OEM.IJOEM_126_18
- Kumar, S. B., Arnipalli, S. R., Mehta, P., Carrau, S., & Ziouzenkova, O. (2022). Iron Deficiency Anemia: Efficacy and Limitations of Nutritional and Comprehensive Mitigation Strategies. *Nutrients*, 14(14), 2976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14142976>
- Kundakovic, M., & Jaric, I. (2017). The Epigenetic Link between Prenatal Adverse Environments and Neurodevelopmental Disorders. *Genes*, 8(3), 104. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes8030104>

- Kushwaha, G., Dozmorov, M., Wren, J. D., Qiu, J., Shi, H., & Xu, D. (2016). Hypomethylation coordinates antagonistically with hypermethylation in cancer development: a case study of leukemia. *Human Genomics*, *10*(S2), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40246-016-0071-5>
- Laine, J. E., Ray, P., Bodnar, W., Cable, P. H., Boggess, K., Offenbacher, S., & Fry, R. C. (2015). Placental Cadmium Levels Are Associated with Increased Preeclampsia Risk. *PLOS ONE*, *10*(9), e0139341. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0139341>
- Lara-Espinoza, C., Carvajal-Millán, E., Balandrán-Quintana, R., López-Franco, Y., & Rascón-Chu, A. (2018). Pectin and Pectin-Based Composite Materials: Beyond Food Texture. *Molecules*, *23*(4), 942. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23040942>
- Li, Y., Xie, C., Murphy, S. K., Skaar, D., Nye, M., Vidal, A. C., ... Hoyo, C. (2016). Lead Exposure during Early Human Development and DNA Methylation of Imprinted Gene Regulatory Elements in Adulthood. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *124*(5), 666–673. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1408577>
- Lobay, D. (2015). Rauwolfia in the Treatment of Hypertension. *Integrative Medicine (Encinitas, Calif.)*, *14*(3), 40–46.
- Lu, G., Xu, H., Chang, D., Wu, Z., Yao, X., Zhang, S., ... Zhang, W. (2014). Arsenic exposure is associated with DNA hypermethylation of the tumor suppressor gene p16. *Journal of Occupational Medicine and Toxicology*, *9*(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12995-014-0042-5>
- Luo, L., Wang, B., Jiang, J., Fitzgerald, M., Huang, Q., Yu, Z., ... Chen, S. (2021). Heavy Metal Contaminations in Herbal Medicines: Determination, Comprehensive Risk Assessments, and Solutions. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, *11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.595335>
- Mahdi, A. A., Ansari, J. A., Agarwal, A., Ahmad, M. K., Siddiqui, S. S., Jafar, T., & Venkatesh, T. (2020). Case of Lead Poisoning Associated with Herbal Health Supplements. *Journal of Health and Pollution*, *10*(28). <https://doi.org/10.5696/2156-9614-10.28.201214>
- Martinez-Zamudio, R., & Ha, H. C. (2011). Environmental epigenetics in metal exposure. *Epigenetics*, *6*(7), 820–827. <https://doi.org/10.4161/epi.6.7.16250>
- McDowell, L. A., Kudaravalli, P., Chen, R. J., & Sticco, K. L. (2024). Iron Overload. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Mejias, S. G., & Ramphul, K. (2023). Penicillamine. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Mendel, R. R. (2013). The Molybdenum Cofactor. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *288*(19), 13165–13172. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.R113.455311>
- Mercadante, A. A., & Kasi, A. (2023). Genetics, Cancer Cell Cycle Phases. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Moffett, D., Smith, C., Stevens, Y.-W., Ingerman, L., Swarts, S., & Chappell, L. (2007). 3 HEALTH EFFECTS. In *Toxicological Profile for Barium and Barium Compounds*. Atlanta, G.A.: Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry.
- Molina-Mesa, S., Martínez-Cendán, J. P., Moyano-Rubiales, D., Cubillas-Rodríguez, I., Molina-García, J., & González-Mesa, E. (2022). Detection of Relevant Heavy Metal Concentrations in Human Placental Tissue: Relationship between the Concentrations of Hg, As, Pb and Cd and the Diet of the Pregnant Woman. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *19*(22), 14731. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192214731>

- Mukhi, S., Rukmini, M. S., Ajay Manjrekar, P., Iyyaswami, R., & Sindhu, H. (2022). Assessment of heavy metals in food and drug packaging materials. *F1000Research*, 11, 648. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.121473.1>
- Mustafa, H. N. (2021). Morphohistometric analysis of the effects of *Coriandrum sativum* on cortical and cerebellar neurotoxicity. *Avicenna Journal of Phytomedicine*, 11(6), 589–598. <https://doi.org/10.22038/AJP.2021.18107>
- Myers, G. J., & Davidson, P. W. (1998). Prenatal methylmercury exposure and children: neurologic, developmental, and behavioral research. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 106(suppl 3), 841–847. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.98106841>
- National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases. (2012). Succimer. In *LiverTox: Clinical and Research Information on Drug-Induced Liver Injury*. Bethesda, M.D.: National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases.
- National Research Council. (1999). 6 Biomarkers of Arsenic Exposure. In *Arsenic in Drinking Water*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/6444>
- National Research Council. (2000). 2 Physiological Role of Copper. In *Copper in Drinking Water*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/9782>
- Nelson, V. R., & Nadeau, J. H. (2010). Transgenerational Genetic Effects. *Epigenomics*, 2(6), 797–806. <https://doi.org/10.2217/epi.10.57>
- Nguyen, H., Pellegrini, M. V., & Gupta, V. (2024). Alpha-Lipoic Acid. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Notterman, D. A., & Mitchell, C. (2015). Epigenetics and Understanding the Impact of Social Determinants of Health. *Pediatric Clinics of North America*, 62(5), 1227–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcl.2015.05.012>
- Ortiz-Garcia, N. Y., Cipriano Ramírez, A. I., Juarez, K., Brand Galindo, J., Briceño, G., & Calderon Martinez, E. (2023). Maternal Exposure to Arsenic and Its Impact on Maternal and Fetal Health: A Review. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.49177>
- Paduraru, E., Iacob, D., Rarinca, V., Rusu, A., Jijie, R., Ilie, O.-D., ... Doroftei, B. (2022). Comprehensive Review Regarding Mercury Poisoning and Its Complex Involvement in Alzheimer's Disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(4), 1992. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23041992>
- Patel, J. B., & Sapra, A. (2023). Nephrotoxic Medications. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Patel, K. T., & Chotai, N. P. (2011). Documentation and Records: Harmonized GMP Requirements. *Journal of Young Pharmacists*, 3(2), 138–150. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-1483.80303>
- Patel, N. B., Xu, Y., McCandless, L. C., Chen, A., Yolton, K., Braun, J., ... Lanphear, B. P. (2019). Very low-level prenatal mercury exposure and behaviors in children: the HOME Study. *Environmental Health*, 18(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-018-0443-5>
- Patwa, J., & Flora, S. J. S. (2020). Heavy Metal-Induced Cerebral Small Vessel Disease: Insights into Molecular Mechanisms and Possible Reversal Strategies. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(11), 3862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21113862>
- Peters, J., & Staff, N. P. (2022). Update on Toxic Neuropathies. *Current Treatment Options in Neurology*, 24(5), 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11940-022-00716-5>
- Plaut, T., & Weiss, L. (2022). Electrodiagnostic Evaluation of Critical Illness Neuropathy. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.

- Porter, J. L., & Rawla, P. (2023). Hemochromatosis. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Posin, S. L., Kong, E. L., & Sharma, S. (2023). Mercury Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Poudyal, B., Shrestha, P., & Chowdhury, Y. S. (2023). Thallium-201. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Priya, A. K., Muruganandam, M., Ali, S. S., & Kornaros, M. (2023). Clean-Up of Heavy Metals from Contaminated Soil by Phytoremediation: A Multidisciplinary and Eco-Friendly Approach. *Toxics*, *11*(5), 422. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics11050422>
- Rahimzadeh, M. R., Rahimzadeh, M. R., Kazemi, S., & Moghadamnia, A. A. (2017). Cadmium toxicity and treatment: An update. *Caspian Journal of Internal Medicine*, *8*(3), 135–145. <https://doi.org/10.22088/CJIM.8.3.135>
- Rajkumar, V., Lee, V. R., & Gupta, V. (2023). Heavy Metal Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Rajput, H. (2014). Effects of Atropa belladonna as an Anti-Cholinergic. *Natural Products Chemistry & Research*, *1*(1). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2329-6836.1000104>
- Ramos, E. M., Oliveira, J., Sobrido, M. J., & Coppola, G. (2017). Primary Familial Brain Calcification. In M. P. Adam, J. Feldman, G. M. Mirzaa, R. A. Pagon, S. E. Wallace, L. J. H. Bean, ... A. Amemiya (Eds.), *GeneReviews® [Internet]*. Seattle, W.A.: University of Washington.
- Rani, P., & Dhok, A. (2023). Effects of Pollution on Pregnancy and Infants. *Cureus*. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.33906>
- Rastogi, S. (2008). Renal effects of environmental and occupational lead exposure. *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, *12*(3), 103. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5278.44689>
- Rebuzzini, P., Fabozzi, G., Cimadomo, D., Ubaldi, F. M., Rienzi, L., Zuccotti, M., & Garagna, S. (2022). Multi- and Transgenerational Effects of Environmental Toxicants on Mammalian Reproduction. *Cells*, *11*(19), 3163. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11193163>
- Reif, B. M., & Murray, B. P. (2024). Chromium Toxicity. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Renuka Gajanan Chawke, Priti Kashinath Jondhale, Vaishnavi Bhagwat Dange, Riya Gokul Chavhan, Ankita P. Jatale, & Swati P. Deshmukh. (2024). Ephedra: An anti-asthamatic medicinal plant. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, *27*(2), 224–229. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.27.2.0182>
- Rísová, V. (2019). The pathway of lead through the mother's body to the child. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology*, *12*(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.2478/intox-2019-0001>
- Rodríguez-Cano, A. M., Calzada-Mendoza, C. C., Estrada-Gutierrez, G., Mendoza-Ortega, J. A., & Perichart-Perera, O. (2020). Nutrients, Mitochondrial Function, and Perinatal Health. *Nutrients*, *12*(7), 2166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12072166>
- Rojas, P., Ruiz-Sánchez, E., Ríos, C., Ruiz-Chow, Á., & Reséndiz-Albor, A. A. (2021). A Health Risk Assessment of Lead and Other Metals in Pharmaceutical Herbal Products and Dietary Supplements Containing Ginkgo biloba in the Mexico City Metropolitan Area. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *18*(16), 8285. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18168285>
- Ruano, C. S. M., Miralles, F., Méhats, C., & Vaiman, D. (2022). The Impact of Oxidative Stress of Environmental Origin on the Onset of Placental Diseases. *Antioxidants*, *11*(1), 106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11010106>

- Ruebner, R. L., Hooper, S. R., Parrish, C., Furth, S. L., & Fadrowski, J. J. (2019). Environmental lead exposure is associated with neurocognitive dysfunction in children with chronic kidney disease. *Pediatric Nephrology*, *34*(11), 2371–2379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00467-019-04306-7>
- Ruiz, L. M., Libedinsky, A., & Elorza, A. A. (2021). Role of Copper on Mitochondrial Function and Metabolism. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences*, *8*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2021.711227>
- Sahu, M. C., Yogeshbhai, M. R., Oza, H., Upadhyay, K., Chanania, K., & Pati, S. (2024). Blood lead levels in pregnant women and their newborn infants at an Indian teaching hospital. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, *13*(1), 348–355. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_963_23
- Sanders, T., Liu, Y., Buchner, V., & Tchounwou, P. B. (2009). Neurotoxic Effects and Biomarkers of Lead Exposure: A Review. *Reviews on Environmental Health*, *24*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1515/REVEH.2009.24.1.15>
- Sardesai, V. M. (1993). Molybdenum: An Essential Trace Element. *Nutrition in Clinical Practice*, *8*(6), 277–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0115426593008006277>
- Sasaki, N., & Carpenter, D. O. (2022). Associations between Metal Exposures and Cognitive Function in American Older Adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *19*(4), 2327. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19042327>
- Sears, M. E. (2013). Chelation: Harnessing and Enhancing Heavy Metal Detoxification—A Review. *The Scientific World Journal*, *2013*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/219840>
- Semelka, R. C., & Ramalho, M. (2023). Gadolinium Deposition Disease: Current State of Knowledge and Expert Opinion. *Investigative Radiology*, *58*(8), 523–529. <https://doi.org/10.1097/RLI.0000000000000977>
- Shahrokhi, M., & Asuncion, R. M. D. (2023). Neurologic Exam. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Shajil, C., & Mahabal, G. D. (2023). Arsenical Keratosis. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Sharma, A., Sharma, V., & Kansal, L. (2010). Amelioration of lead induced hepatotoxicity by Allium sativum. *Libyan Journal of Medicine*, *5*. <https://doi.org/10.4176/091107>
- Sherief, L. M., Rifky, E., Attia, M., Ahmed, R., Kamal, N. M., Oshi, M. A. M., & Hanna, D. (2022). Platinum-induced ototoxicity in pediatric cancer survivors: GSTP1 c.313A>G variant association. *Medicine*, *101*(45), e31627. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000031627>
- Silberman, J., Galuska, M. A., & Taylor, A. (2023). Activated Charcoal. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Škubník, J., Pavlíčková, V. S., Ruml, T., & Rimpelová, S. (2021). Vincristine in Combination Therapy of Cancer: Emerging Trends in Clinics. *Biology*, *10*(9), 849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology10090849>
- Speer, R. M., Zhou, X., Volk, L. B., Liu, K. J., & Hudson, L. G. (2023). Chapter Six - Arsenic and cancer: Evidence and mechanisms. In *Advances in pharmacology* (Vol. 96, pp. 151–202). <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.apha.2022.08.001>
- States, J. C., Srivastava, S., Chen, Y., & Barchowsky, A. (2009). Arsenic and Cardiovascular Disease. *Toxicological Sciences*, *107*(2), 312–323. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfn236>
- Stepanyan, A., Petrackova, A., Hakobyan, S., Savara, J., Davitavyan, S., Kriegova, E., & Arakelyan, A. (2023). Long-term environmental metal exposure is associated with hypomethylation of CpG sites in NFKB1 and other genes related to oncogenesis. *Clinical Epigenetics*, *15*(1), 126. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13148-023-01536-3>

- Subbarao, B. S., Silverman, A., & Eapen, B. C. (2023). Seizure Medications. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Tchounwou, P. B., Yedjou, C. G., Patlolla, A. K., & Sutton, D. J. (2012). Heavy Metal Toxicity and the Environment. In A. Luch (Ed.), *Molecular, Clinical and Environmental Toxicology* (Vol. 3, pp. 133–164). Basel: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7643-8340-4_6
- Thomason, M. E., Hect, J. L., Rauh, V. A., Trentacosta, C., Wheelock, M. D., Eggebrecht, A. T., ... Burt, S. A. (2019). Prenatal lead exposure impacts cross-hemispheric and long-range connectivity in the human fetal brain. *NeuroImage*, *191*, 186–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.02.017>
- Todd, G. D., Keith, S., Faroon, O., Buser, M., Ingerman, L., Citra, M., ... Nguyen, A. (2020). CHAPTER 5 POTENTIAL FOR HUMAN EXPOSURE. In *Toxicological Profile for Molybdenum*. Atlanta, G.A.: Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry.
- Tracy, J. W., Guo, A., Liang, K., Bartram, J., & Fisher, M. (2020). Sources of and Solutions to Toxic Metal and Metalloid Contamination in Small Rural Drinking Water Systems: A Rapid Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(19), 7076. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17197076>
- Tsai, K.-F., Hsu, P.-C., Kung, C.-T., Lee, C.-T., You, H.-L., Huang, W.-T., ... Lee, W.-C. (2021). The Risk Factors of Blood Cadmium Elevation in Chronic Kidney Disease. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *18*(23), 12337. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182312337>
- Tsoi, M. F., Lo, C. W. H., Cheung, T. T., & Cheung, B. M. Y. (2021). Blood lead level and risk of hypertension in the United States National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 1999–2016. *Scientific Reports*, *11*(1), 3010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82435-6>
- Tumolo, M., Ancona, V., De Paola, D., Losacco, D., Campanale, C., Massarelli, C., & Uricchio, V. F. (2020). Chromium Pollution in European Water, Sources, Health Risk, and Remediation Strategies: An Overview. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(15), 5438. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155438>
- Wai, K., Mar, O., Kosaka, S., Umemura, M., & Watanabe, C. (2017). Prenatal Heavy Metal Exposure and Adverse Birth Outcomes in Myanmar: A Birth-Cohort Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *14*(11), 1339. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14111339>
- Wang, Hongting, Chen, Y., Wang, L., Liu, Q., Yang, S., & Wang, C. (2023). Advancing herbal medicine: enhancing product quality and safety through robust quality control practices. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, *14*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1265178>
- Wang, Hua, Liu, L., Hu, Y.-F., Hao, J.-H., Chen, Y.-H., Su, P.-Y., ... Xu, D.-X. (2016). Maternal serum cadmium level during pregnancy and its association with small for gestational age infants: a population-based birth cohort study. *Scientific Reports*, *6*(1), 22631. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep22631>
- Weaver, B. A. (2014). How Taxol/paclitaxel kills cancer cells. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*, *25*(18), 2677–2681. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.e14-04-0916>
- Wei, S., Zhang, H., & Tao, S. (2019). A review of arsenic exposure and lung cancer. *Toxicology Research*, *8*(3), 319–327. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8TX00298C>
- Wessels, I., Maywald, M., & Rink, L. (2017). Zinc as a Gatekeeper of Immune Function. *Nutrients*, *9*(12), 1286. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu9121286>
- Wilbur, S., Abadin, H., Fay, M., Yu, D., Tencza, B., Ingerman, L., ... James, S. (2012). 3 HEALTH EFFECTS. In *Toxicological Profile for Chromium*. Atlanta, G.A.: Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry.

Xiao, S., Wu, P., Han, L., & Liu, X. (2023). [Analysis of disease burden of lung cancer attributable to chromium in Chinese population from 1990 to 2019]. *Zhonghua Lao Dong Wei Sheng Zhi Ye Bing Za Zhi = Zhonghua Laodong Weisheng Zhiyebing Zazhi = Chinese Journal of Industrial Hygiene and Occupational Diseases*, 41(11), 825–831. <https://doi.org/10.3760/CMA.J.CN121094-20221206-00587>

Yen, C., Lin, C.-L., & Chiang, M.-C. (2023). Exploring the Frontiers of Neuroimaging: A Review of Recent Advances in Understanding Brain Functioning and Disorders. *Life*, 13(7), 1472. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life13071472>

Zhang, C., Xu, C., Gao, X., & Yao, Q. (2022). Platinum-based drugs for cancer therapy and anti-tumor strategies. *Theranostics*, 12(5), 2115–2132. <https://doi.org/10.7150/thno.69424>